

Development of the Marketing Strategy to Boost Wedang Sirih Rempah Product Market Share

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ABSTRACT: *Wedang Sirih Rempah*, is a herbal beverage prepared from herbal spices produced by one herbal beverages company in Central Java Province, Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to identify internal and external elements as well as alternative and priority strategies for marketing the new product *Wedang Sirih Rempah*. This study used descriptive qualitative and quantitative approaches and was conducted from January to June 2023. CV Mamigus Restu Bagus was used as the company case study. Purposive sampling was employed to identify study locations, and purposive sampling was also utilized to pick respondents. Primary data and secondary data were utilized as supporting data. The data collected through observation and direct interviews with the company's key informants were then described using a qualitative descriptive method. While the data acquired through surveys with key informants and supporting informants were examined quantitatively using SWOT analysis and QSPM. The findings of the interviews and observations yielded the factors of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. The findings of data analysis suggested that the priority strategy in marketing *Wedang Sirih Rempah* was to perform and increase offline and online promotions through social media and marketplaces, with the maximum TAS score of 6.54. That was, this strategy then be proposed to the corporation for use in the marketing of *Wedang Sirih Rempah* in order to increase the market share of the company.

KEYWORDS: Marketing strategy, QSPM, SWOT, *Wedang Sirih Rempah*.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the countries with the highest biological diversity in the world. This is demonstrated by the fact that the country is home to more than 30,000 different plant species, 960 of which have been identified as medicinal plants and 283 of which are important for the traditional medicine industry (Retno, 2018). Medicinal plants and herbal spices have now been widely developed as processed herbal product, such as functional herbal food and drink that can be consumed by people in today's modern era. Every region in Indonesia has its own culinary drink with the same basic ingredients. This business has a lot of potential and chances since it can attract both local and foreign tourists because Indonesian cuisine is distinctive and has its own taste and originality (Rian, 2013). One of the functional herbal drinks made from herbal spices with the main ingredient betel leaf is *Wedang Sirih Rempah*, produced by CV Mamigus Restu Bagus, one of the Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Indonesia.

In order to boost business income, the presence of good potential and opportunities in the field of herbal product business must be accompanied by the adoption of suitable and relevant marketing techniques. The 9P marketing mix approach (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Process, People, Physical Evidence, Payment, and Packaging) will be used to implement the marketing strategy in this research. One marketing strategy is a marketing mix to promote products or services and includes information clearly, so that it can encourage customers to give and make preferences for the image or impression of a product (Hamsal and Eva Sundari, 2022).

The *Wedang Sirih Rempah* product was developed and launched by CV Mamigus Restu Bagus in response to the availability of betel leaves, which are currently abundant, particularly in their own gardens and among their partner farmers. The product has a competitive pricing strategy and features a packaging design that is more contemporary in comparison to its industry counterparts. In addition to this, there is a limited presence of herbal beverage offerings derived from betel leaves among existing market participants and competitors.

CV Mamigus Restu Bagus has effectively penetrated the marketplace of Shopee, achieving a favorable rating and successfully venturing into the export market for certain products. However, it might be argued that this company has not effectively executed an appropriate marketing plan for promoting its new product both offline and online. The lack of promotional advertising content and comprehensive information regarding new items contributes to a limited familiarity among individuals with the *Wedang Sirih Rempah* product. The newly introduced items a range of offerings that have been on the market for duration of 1-1.5 years. Marketing

offline not yet said to be optimal because it is only 1 reseller alone took and marketed them out of a total of 50 resellers who is a partners of CV Mamigus Restu Bagus, the number of *Wedang Sirih Rempah* products taken reseller even though it is still relatively small, only around 500 pcs in a span of 2 to 3 months. Plus, marketing online CV Mamigus Restu Bagus is still focused on Marketplace Shopee only so that potential buyers only know and buy products with a large number of sales and their relation to the perception of buyers who are still inclined to buy products that have been sold a lot rather than buying new products. *Wedang Sirih Rempah* products have only sold 220 pcs since the release and upload Of Shopee in June 2022 to date. This phenomenon leads to an increase in sales of the company's established items or those that have a long-standing presence in the market while limiting the sales of new products. Consequently, it becomes challenging to penetrate product categories that have already experienced significant sales.

The purpose of this study was to identify internal and external factors as well as alternative and priority strategies for marketing the new product *Wedang Sirih Rempah*.

LITERATUR REVIEW HERBAL DRINK

An herbal drink is a drink product that has health benefits for the body it is generally consumed by brewing it using a mixture of water, the ingredients for making an herbal drink come from parts of medicinal plants or herbal spices, which consist of leaves, stems, flowers, roots, to fruit or seeds. The efficacy of herbal drinks lies in the content of natural bioactive compounds or components such as carotenoids, phenolic acids, flavonoids, coumarins, alkaloids, polyacetylenes, saponins, terpenoids, and others. The herbal ingredients used in the formulation of these drinks are usually processed in various ways, starting from sorting and grading, washing, drying, refining and reducing size to increase shelf life, to packaging. Therefore, herbal beverage products that are sold on the market (commercial) are available in various forms such as whole parts of the dried plant or dry ingredients, dry powder, and drinks that are ready to be consumed immediately (Chandrasekara & Shahidi, 2018).

Wedang Sirih Rempah is one of functional herbal drink produced by CV Mamigus Restu Bagus. It is made from herbal spices, including betel leaves, clove leaves, secang, ginger, turmeric, temulawak, fennel, pandan leaves, and rock sugar, each of which has health benefits. all parts of the betel plant contain arecoline, which helps relieve snoring, increase peristaltic motion, and stimulate the central nervous system and cognitive function (Samirana et al., 2017).

MARKETING MIX 9P

The marketing mix refers to a collection of marketing strategies and tactics employed by corporations or corporate entities in a consistent manner to effectively attain their marketing objectives, particularly in terms of market share (Ningrum, 2020). The marketing mix initially consisted of four linked and significant variables, generally referred to as the 4P's (product, pricing, location, promotion). These factors were widely recognized and utilized in various marketing operations. Nevertheless, due to the progression of society and technological advancements, the components of the marketing mix are progressively expanding to include 7P (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Process, People, Physical Evidence) and 9P, incorporating additional factors such as Payment and Packaging. These additions are observed in both marketing actions and the evaluation of customer satisfaction levels.

The concept of the marketing mix was redefined to be more applicable so that the marketing mix became 9 elements (9P). These elements include Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Process, People, Physical Evidence, Payment, and Packaging (Ningrum, 2020).

ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

A. Internal Environmental

The business environment that exists within a company or organization is known as the internal environment. This environment consists of factors that have an impact on business performance, one of which is how marketing plans and strategies are made. The strengths and weaknesses of the company are found and reflected in the internal environment.

Human resources, product marketing or distribution, the company's financial situation, company production and operations, and business or company research and development are all functional areas that become variables and must be taken into account when analyzing or evaluating the internal environment (Retno, 2018).

B. External Environmental

The business environment that is outside the control of the company or organization is known as the external environment. This

environment consists of opportunities and threats that have the potential to affect performance and hinder company operations. Analysis of the external environment is a factor that can influence in determining the preparation of plans and formulation of marketing strategies for a product and these factors are beyond the company's control, so that in conducting an analysis of the company's external environment it is necessary to identify a list of opportunities and threats that affect the company. In addition, this analysis of the company's external environment also influences the determination of the strategy to be taken by taking advantage of the company's opportunities and avoiding various threats that harm or hinder the company (Fauzan, 2022).

SWOT ANALYSIS

The process of determining the formulation of corporate strategy involves identifying various factors that are arranged coherently or systematically. Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, and Threats stands for SWOT analysis. The purpose of using a SWOT analysis is to maximize the strengths of a company or organization in order to take advantage of existing opportunities while minimizing its weaknesses and threats. A strategic planning technique called SWOT analysis is used to evaluate a company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. The following steps are steps to be taken when conducting a SWOT analysis to ensure that the results are more precise and appropriate (Retno, 2018).

QSPM

Level decisions or the final stage of strategy preparation and formulation is commonly known as the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM). QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matriks) is used to evaluate the strategies that have been analyzed previously by combining the formulation of internal and external factors of the company. Conceptually, QSPM sets out the main internal and external factors to determine the relative attractiveness of the various strategies (Akbar et al., 2022).

The final step in developing a plan is to use the QSPM matrix to identify the best strategy or priority from the SWOT Matrix results. The availability of this QSPM matrix can be utilized to sort and weight existing strategies for use as a priority scale in strategy execution. This stage demonstrates and generates priority strategies or the best alternative strategies from variations of the previous strategies chosen to be executed by the company (Mujiastuti et al., 2019).

MARKETING

Marketing is a social and managerial activity both individuals and groups in obtaining what they need by making, promoting and selling products to other people who are referred to as customers (Furqon, 2019).

Activities aimed at applying internal situations, such as product, price, promotion, location, and marketing channels, to achieve effective results are also included in the definition of marketing. That is, marketing management is a process that involves analysis, planning, implementation, and control of goods, services, and ideas or concepts that depend on the exchange or sales process with the aim of achieving customer satisfaction (Prayudi & Yulistria, 2020).

A marketing strategy is a collection of business plans that outlines a company's approach to achieving its marketing objectives through various methods and then combined into one strategy, which is more commonly referred to as the marketing mix (Furqon, 2019).

When developing a marketing strategy, analytical methods are needed. Analysis of a number of factors is needed so that a company's marketing strategy can respond to any changes in market conditions and cost factors, namely environmental, market, competition, capability analysis, consumer behavior, and economic factors (Prayudi & Yulistria, 2020).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

CV Mamigus Restu Bagus is a company that processes spices into whole spices, powders, teas, drinks, traditional cuisines, herbs, and other processed products. *Wedang Sirih Rempah* is one of CV Mamigus Restu Bagus's new product developments, in which several herbal spices have been employed as *Simplicia*, including betel leaf, ginger, clove leaf, turmeric, pandan leaf, fennel, curcuma, rock sugar. CV Mamigus has not executed a good offline or online marketing plan for this new product, *Wedang Sirih Rempah*.

The 9P marketing mix approach was used to conduct the analysis (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, Process, People, Physical Evidence, Payment, and Packaging). The findings of the marketing strategy formulation will be weighted, with the US value

(Attractive Scores) and the TAS value (Total Attractive Scores) calculated utilizing a decision-making process or tool, namely QSPM. The company will thereafter receive a priority marketing plan for *Wedang Sirih Rempah* items. The company is projected to be able to improve sales volume and revenue with this plan by employing a marketing strategy that is appropriate for the company's circumstances.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at CV Mamigus Restu Bagus which is engaged in the herbal spice simplicia business and herbal products located in Karanganyar Village, Kontakmacan District, Sragen Regency, Central Java. The research was carried out from January 2023 to June 2023. The research location was chosen on the basis of (purposive), namely businesses engaged in the field of biopharmaceuticals, particularly herbal products made from herbal spices and medicinal plants used as simplicia. Another thing to consider is that the company is developing a new product called "*Wedang Sirih Rempah*" and does not yet have the right marketing strategy to market its product.

This study used both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Purposive sampling was used to choose respondents, and it was assumed that the respondent or informant knew about and was involved in the marketing efforts of CV Mamigus Restu Bagus. Use informants and respondents from both inside and outside the company to figure out the group. A key informant from the internal business, included 1 owner or manager of CV Mamigus Restu Bagus, 1 manager, 1 employee in marketing, and 5 workers in production. Respondents or supporting sources come from outside the business. They include one person who sells *Wedang Sirih Rempah* and 31 people who have bought and used it. The primary data for this study came from observations, interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs), and questionnaires given to respondents. The secondary data came from journals, e-books, previous research, and other agencies connected to this research. This study used observation, interviews, focus groups, and a Likert scale form to gather data. This study's Likert scale has four possible answers: SS for "strongly agree," S for "agree," TS for "disagree," and STS for "strongly disagree" (Mulyani, 2021).

Data analysis techniques used descriptive and qualitative methods to describe and explain the results of the identification of IFAS (strengths - weaknesses) and EFAS (opportunities - threats) and quantitative methods for evaluating and evaluating the IFE and EFE matrices and the QSPM matrix when coming up with different strategies and strategic priorities for CV Mamigus Restu Good. In the process of putting together and planning CV Mamigus Restu Bagus's marketing strategy, there are several stages of data analysis.

A. Input Level

The input stage, namely by identifying and analyzing IFAS which includes strengths and weaknesses, and EFAS which includes opportunities and threats that CV Mamigus Restu Bagus has. Then do the assessment and weighting of each internal and external factors using the IFE and EFE matrices.

B. Matching Stage

The matching stage uses the SWOT matrix to formulate strategies and uses the SWOT matrix quadrants (coordinate points) to determine the company's position.

C. Decision Level

The decision stage uses the QSPM matrix to sort and weight existing strategies to be used as a priority scale in strategy implementation. Then the FGD was carried out (Focus Group Discussion) with CV Mamigus to determine several alternative strategies that will be used as an implementation plan in marketing *Wedang Sirih Rempah*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH OBJECT

CV Mamigus Restu Bagus is an MSME engaged in the field of processed spice plants in the form of whole spices, powder, tea, traditional drinks and food, herbs and other processed products. This company was founded and managed by the family of Mrs. Mamik Windiarti. All products already have PIRT permits and halal certificates so product quality and safety are guaranteed. CV Mamigus Restu Bagus has established partnerships in supporting the supply of raw materials for production, including the Sunan Kalijaga Agricultural Training Center, KWT Tani Mulyo, KWT Banaran, KWT Gringging, Mina Ikan Jatisongo Group, Purworejo Palm Sugar Business Group. CV Mamigus also distributes and distributes its products to distributors, resellers and drop shippers, as well as retailers.

The marketing process at CV Mamigus Restu Bagus is carried out automatically offline in the local area alone covers the area of Sragen Regency and follows various event exhibitions and marketing online through social media and marketplace, that is Tiktok, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Shopee. Export markets have also been explored and have succeeded in entering the markets of several countries, namely exports to Malaysia, Singapore, the Philippines, Thailand and China with a total sales of 50 to 200 packages per month. One of the new products whose sales level is still low, around 220 pcs since its release in June 2022, is *Wedang Sirih Rempah*. *Wedang Sirih Rempah* is a herbal beverage product made from a variety of herbal spice compositions that have been used as simplicial, including betel leaf, ginger, clove leaf, turmeric, pandan leaf, fennel, Curcuma, and rock sugar.

SWOT ANALYSIS

A. Identify IFAS dan EFAS

The results of the identification of IFAS (internal factors) and EFAS (external factors) at CV Mamigus Restu Bagus through the 9P marketing mix approach are as follows.

Table 1. Identification of IFAS

Internal Factors	Strengths	Weakness
Product	1. Quality products and always available.	
Price	1. Prices are affordable and in accordance with the quality of the product.	
Place	1. The location of the company is in a residential area and is easily accessible. 2. The location is comfortable and kept clean.	1. Limited business facilities.
Promotion		1. Lack of promotion and information of new products. 2. Product display in the marketplace and social media is not yet attractive.

People	1. Employees are good, neat, nimble and responsible.	1. Lack of personnel or employees in the marketing department.
Physical evidence	1. The product has proven its efficacy and the composition of the ingredients is in accordance with what is stated on the product packaging.	1. There is no written cooperation contract with the partners.
Process	1. The ordering and complaint service process is fast and responsive. 2. Accept returns/exchanges of damaged or inappropriate products and packaging.	
Payment	1. The payment process is fast and easy to understand	
Packaging	1. Attractive and safe product packaging protects the product.	

Table 2. Identification of EFAS

External Factor	Opportunity	Threats
Product	1. Abundant and easily available raw materials. 2. The demand for simplicia products and herbal spices continues to increase.	1. Similar product competitors.
Price		1. Price competition for similar products. 2. Increase in raw material prices.
Place	1. Platform digital increasingly popular.	
Promotion	1. Purchase of products by online increasingly popular. 2. The wider the marketing the better offline, online, as well as export market opportunities.	
People		
Physical evidence	1. Partners who can maintain and foster good cooperative relationships. 2. Many parties are interested in partnering with Mamigus.	1. Handling and treatment of raw materials from partners not according to SOP.
Process		
Payment		
Packaging		

B. Matrices IFE dan EFE

The stages in conducting an evaluation analysis of the IFE and EFE matrices are as follows (Rangkuti, 2015).

- 1) Determine the important factors of the internal and external conditions of a company or business unit to be studied (column1), then arrange and classify them in each column based on strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.
- 2) The value of the level of importance of each factor is commonly referred to as the weight (column 3) which is the factor category that is considered very important (weight 1,0) to not too important (weight 0,0), by dividing the total value of the significance level by the respective significance level -each factor, then the weighting results are obtained.
- 3) In accordance with the conditions of the company, assign a rating or value to each of the internal and external factors (column4). Score 4 indicates very good condition, value 3 indicates good condition, value 2 indicates normal condition/ordinary weakness, and value 1 indicates poor condition/main weakness on the internal condition scale. Factors with values 2 and 1 are included in the weakness category, while factors with values 3 and 4 are only included in the Strength category. A value of 4 for external conditions indicates a major/extraordinary opportunity, a value of 3 indicates an ordinary opportunity, a value of 2 indicates a

moderate threat, and a value of 1 indicates a major threat.

- 4) The weighting or score in column 5 is the multiplication of the rating and the weight. The IFE and EFE values of the business mentioned above can be determined and known by adding up all these values.

Table 3. Evaluation of Internal Factors

	Internal factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Strength				
1	Quality products and always available.	0.10	3.50	0.35
2	Prices are affordable and in accordance with the quality of the product.	0.08	3.30	0.25
3	The location of the company is in a residential area and is easily accessible.	0.08	3.36	0.26
4	The location is comfortable and kept clean.	0.05	3.40	0.17
5	Employees are good, neat, nimble and responsible.	0.08	3.30	0.25
6	The product has proven its efficacy and the composition of the ingredients is in accordance with what is stated on the product packaging.	0.08	3.28	0.26
7	The process of ordering service and responding to customer complaints is fast and responsive.	0.08	3.26	0.25
8	Accept returns/exchanges of damaged or inappropriate products and packaging.	0.08	3.26	0.25
9	The payment process is fast and easy to understand.	0.08	3.28	0.25
10	The product packaging is attractive and safe to protect the product.	0.08	3.15	0.24
	Total			2.52

Weakness

1	Limited business facilities.	0.03	2.90	0.07
2	Lack of promotion and information of new products.	0.09	2.50	0.22
3	Product display in marketplace and social media is not yet attractive.	0.08	2.50	0.19
4	There is no written cooperation contract with the partners.	0.05	2.90	0.15
5	Lack of personnel or marketing department employees.	0.07	2.50	0.18
	Total		1.00	0.76
	Total X (Difference in IFE scores)			1.58

Based on the IFE matrix above, it can be seen that CV Mamigus Restu Bagus has 11 strengths and 4 weaknesses. The total score obtained from all strength factors is 2.52. While the total score obtained from all the weakness factors is equal to 0.76. Therefore, the results of the internal factor value or X value of 1.58 are obtained from the difference between the total score of strengths and the total score of weaknesses.

Table 4. Evaluation of External Factors

External Factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Peluang			
1Abundant and easily available raw materials.	0.13	3.40	0.44
2The demand for simplicia products and herbal spices continues to increase.	0.10	3.00	0.29
3Platform digital increasingly popular.	0.10	3.50	0.34
4Purchase of products by online increasingly popular.	0.10	3.50	0.34
5The wider the marketing the better offline, online, as well as export market opportunities.	0.10	3.50	0.34
6Partners who can maintain and foster good cooperative relationships.	0.10	3.20	0.31
7Many parties are interested in partnering with CV Mamigus.	0.10	3.20	0.31
Total			2.36
Threats			
1Similar product competitors.	0.10	1.50	0.15
2Price competition for similar products.	0.10	2.00	0.19
3Increase in raw material prices.	0.03	1.90	0.06
4Handling and treatment of raw materials from partners not according to SOP.	0.06	2.00	0.06
Total	1.00		0.46
Total Y(Difference in EFE value)			1.84

Based on the EFE matrix above, it is known that CV Mamigus Restu Bagus has 7 opportunity factors and 4 threat factors obtained from data collection. The total score obtained from all opportunity factors is 2.36. While the total score obtained from all threatfactors is equal to 0.46. Therefore, the results of the external factor value or Y value of 1.84 are obtained from the difference between the total opportunity score and the total threat score.

C. SWOT Matrix

The following is a SWOT matrix compiled based on the internal and external factors that exist in CV Mamigus Restu Bagus.

Table 5. SWOT Matrix

SO	WO
Conduct and improve promotions offline and online through social media and marketplace (S1,S2,S3,S4,S5,S6,S7,S8,S9,S10,O1,O2,O3,O4,O5)	Improve production facilities and locations to increase production volume (W1,O1,O2).
Increasing market share both local and export (S1, S2, S3, S6, S9, S10, O1, O2, O3, O4, O5, O6, O7).	Improve the appearance of existing products in marketplace and social media to make it more interesting (W2,W3,O3,O4,O5).
Improve and expand partnership or collaboration networks (S1, S2, S6, S10, O1, O6, O7).	Conducting MoU with partners and monitoring partner progress (W4,O6,O7).
	Add and recruit marketing department employees (W2,W3,W5,O3, O4,O5).

ST	WT
Strengthen product branding (S1, S2, S6, S8, S10, T1, T2).	Conduct socialization and coaching to partner farmers regarding the implementation of GAP and GHP (W4, T1, T4).
Add partner farmers to produce raw materials (S1, S6, T3).	Maintain good communication with partners so that a harmonious partnership is established (W3, W4, T4).
Increase supervision of raw materials from partner farmers (S1, S2, T1, T4).	

D. SWOT Matrix Quadrant

Next, determine the company's position using the SWOT matrix quadrants or determining coordinate points. This aims to determine the location of the marketing strategy for *Wedang Sirih Rempah* products. Based on the IFE and EFE matrix tables, the internal factor value (X) is 1.58 and the external factor value (Y) is 1.84. The location of the coordinate points can be seen in the image below.

Figure 2. SWOT Matrix Quadrant

Based on the results of the SWOT matrix quadrant analysis above, it can be seen that the company's position is in quadrant 1. This means that the company is in very good and profitable condition because it is able to take advantage of existing opportunities using its strengths. The strategy to be implemented is an aggressive strategy in encouraging and supporting the growth and development of the company.

QSPM

The QSPM matrix is the last stage of decision-making to determine the priority strategy of the alternative strategies that have been prepared. The TAS value is obtained by multiplying the weight value of each factor with the AS value. The US value is the attractiveness value obtained from the results of discussions with the company and the filling is also carried out with the company. The results of the QSPM analysis are as follows.

Table 6. QSPM Analysis Results

	Strategy Arrangement	Score	Rank
1.	Conduct and improve promotions offline and online through social media and marketplace.	6.63	1
2.	Strengthen product branding.	6.49	2
3.	Improve and expand the network of partnerships or cooperation.	6.38	3
4.	Increasing market share both local and export.	6.31	4
5.	Improve the appearance of existing products in marketplace and social media to make it more interesting.	6.29	5

6.	Producing raw materials themselves by adding partner farmers.	6.16	6
7.	Conducting MoU with partners and monitoring partner progress.	6.11	7
8.	Increase supervision on raw materials from partner farmers.	6.08	8
9.	Add and recruit employees in the marketing department.	6.06	9
10.	Conduct outreach and guidance to partner farmers regarding the implementation of GAP and GHP.	5.71	10
11.	Improve production facilities and locations to increase production volume.	5.33	11
12.	Improve the appearance of existing products in marketplace and social media to make it interesting.	5.29	12

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the calculation of the highest TAS total value is 6.54, namely the strategy of conducting and increasing promotions offline and online through social media and marketplace. Therefore, this strategy is the most appropriate or most prioritized strategy that is recommended to be implemented as a marketing strategy for *Wedang Sirih Rempah*.

ALTERNATIVE STRATEGIES BASED ON COMPANY FGD

The FGD was then carried out (Focus Group Discussion) with CV Mamigus to determine several alternative strategies that are considered more important than all the strategies obtained and will be used as an implementation plan in the marketing of *Wedang Sirih Rempah*. The alternative strategy is as follows.

Table 7. Alternative Choice Strategies

No.	Selected Alternative Strategy
1.	Conduct and improve promotions offline and online.
2.	Strengthen product branding.
3.	Increasing market share both local and export.
—	<u>Improve the appearance of existing products in marketplace and social media to make it</u>
4.	<u>more interesting.</u>

Based on the results of the FGD with the company, alternative strategic priorities were obtained, namely conducting and increasing promotions offline and online. This means that the priority strategy obtained from the results of the QSPM analysis is in accordance with the desired strategy and will be implemented by the company.

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Based on the results of the analysis using the QSPM matrix and the company's FGD, priority strategies and five alternative strategies are obtained that can be implemented by the company. Furthermore, the implementation plan of the priority strategies and alternative strategies at CV Mamigus Restu Bagus obtained from the QSPM and FGD analysis is as follows.

Table 8. Implementation Plan

No. Problems	Results of the Strategy lation from the FGD	Implementation Plan	PIC	Time span
1. Lack of promotion is good offline and online (platform digital) on the new product <i>Wedang Sirih Rempah</i> so that	Conduct and improve promotions offline andonline.	Promotion offline by following various event exhibition. Promotion online through social media and marketplace to build access for consumers. Creating attractive promotional content containing product information photos and videos, especially	Marketing managers and employee	ocus up to 1 year ahead

people are not aware of the information about the new product.		new products which include product presentation methods, natural herbal ingredients, product properties, and so on with attention to layout, color, background, audio, and attractive effects.	s.
2. There are several competitors with similar products and the same or almost the same price.	ngthen product branding.	Displaying memorable and attractive brand and packaging designs, superior product quality, promotions and advertisements on social media, participating in exhibitions, and you can also create interesting content that contains product information and advantages.	Owner and manager 'ocus up to 1 year ahead
3. Sales volume of <i>Wedang Sirih Rempah</i> products is still low and only has 1 partner reseller only for this product.	Increasing market share both local and export.	Expansion of market share by adding relations or partners reseller, dropshipper, and retailers in various places to make it easier for consumers to know and get products.	Owner and manager 'ocus up to 1 year ahead
4. Display of <i>Wedang Sirih Rempah</i> products on social media and marketplace not interesting yet.	Improve the appearance of existing products in marketplace and social media to make it more interesting.	Improve the appearance of its products on social media and marketplace by adding unique variations to product photos as is background herbal spice ingredients, photos and videos of the composition of the herbal spice ingredients, and photos or videos of how to prepare <i>Wedang Sirih</i> .	Marketing managers and employee 'ocus up to 1 year ahead

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The main internal strength of CV Mamigus Restu Bagus was its high-quality *Wedang Sirih Rempah* products, which were always available and had a unique taste and smell. The freshness of the ingredients was also kept up. While the biggest problem was that there isn't enough advertising and information about new products. On external factors, which include the main possibilities for CV Mamigus Restu Bagus, which were marketing opportunities offline, online, and in export markets, the bigger the market, the better. While competitors and price competition for similar products were the major threats.
2. Alternative strategies based on FGD with companies and strategies found in the SWOT matrix, such as doing and increasing offline and online promotions, strengthening product branding, increasing both local and export market share, and improving the look of existing products in the marketplace and on social media to make them more interesting.
3. The most important strategy that CV Mamigus Restu Bagus can use for *Wedang Sirih Rempah* products was to promote offline and online through social media and marketplaces by creating attractive content displays that consumers can understand and that make them want to buy products.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The priority strategy that has been obtained from the QSPM matrix analysis is expected to be implemented by companies for business development by carrying out and increasing promotion on an ongoing basis offline and online through social media and marketplace so that it can increase sales volume, especially *Wedang Sirih Rempah* products.
2. It is better if the company can do more intensive marketing and promotion online by using platforms digital it has, considering that the majority of customers are more interested in shopping online.
3. The company should be able to maintain product quality and improve production facilities and layout to support production activities.

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